

**CORPORATE SOLVENCY AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF
MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The study investigated corporate solvency and financial performance of selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria from 2012 to 2021. Secondary data obtained from selected manufacturing companies were used for the study. Data obtained were analyzed with multiple regression techniques. Empirical results obtained showed that working capital management and debt/equity have a positive influence on financial performance measured by return on asset (ROA). The study therefore recommends that liquidity management should be improved upon to enhance the financial performance of manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Keywords: Working capital management, Return on asset, Debt/Equity ratio, Current ratio, Operational efficiency

1.0 Introduction

Industry and market globalisation has given rise to new businesses, granted avenues for growth and development and this led to some businesses closing or being acquired by more successful companies. Decisions on divestiture from non-profitable activities and mergers are also being taken as a precaution against the causes of the company's insolvency. The economy is not favourable at times and can render companies that have not planned strategically on how to mitigate this issue when it could have arisen at risk. The profitability and solvency are conditioned by the company's strategy. The company's growth brings a progressive increase in financial needs for the operational cycle, leading to a change in the solvency capacity (AlGhusin, 2015).

Financial performance means the evaluation of profitability and financial strength of an organization to determine the strengths and weaknesses of the firm being appraised. The objective of any firm is to maximize the wealth of its shareholders. This objective will be achieved if the organisation makes a profit. An increase in the market value of a firm is an indicator of financial performance (Kakanda et al, 2016). Financial performance is key to an organisation as it leads to an increasing market value of a firm. Investors are usually interested in the financial performance of a firm because it will assist them in making wise investment decisions that will invariably maximize their wealth. Assessment of determinants of financial performance of a firm has attracted the attention of researchers in corporate finance literature.

Thus, financial performance which is the focus of this study measures the results of firms in terms of return on assets. Because of the desire to improve and increase the profitability of a firm to meet the aspirations of the stakeholders, the financial performance of a firm has become the major factor of evaluating the success or otherwise of a firm (Kwaghfan, 2015). A major issue in business is operating a performance management system that will help managers make valuable decisions to improve shareholder's wealth. Although these management systems are subject to various risks of inefficiency, insolvency, illiquidity, etc. Problems also arise from increased pressure on manufacturing to make phenomenal profit surpassing that of its rivals in the industry. In the process of doing this, there is a tendency for these organizations to get careless in resource management particularly the management of liquidity and efficiency (Khidmat & Rehman, 2014). With the decline in the manufacturing sector due to the fluctuating exchange rate, organisations have been led to implement aggressive sales policies, cost cuts and other activities aimed at beating the competition in the market. This can lead to loss of focus and the goals of the organisations.

Statement of the Problem

The major issue in business is operating performance management which will help managers make valuable decisions to improve shareholders' wealth. With the closure of manufacturing companies in Nigeria due to the high cost incurred on the purchase of fuel to supply electricity, high exchange rates as well as insecurity organizations have been forced to implement aggressive sales policies and cut costs.

Research Objective:

To consider the influence of corporate solvency on the return on assets of manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange.

Research Question

What is the impact of corporate solvency on the return on assets of manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange?

Research Hypothesis

Corporate solvency does not influence the return on assets of manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange.

and embark on other activities to survive in the Nigerian market.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Corporate Solvency

Corporate solvency is the ability of a company to have enough assets in its possession to cover its liabilities. It can also be seen as the ability of an organisation to meet its long-term obligations in the case of liquidation. The solvency directly relates to the statement of the financial position of the business in terms of its viability and its capabilities to meet long-term obligations. According to Murray (2016) solvency measures the relationship between the items that the business owns i.e. assets and what the business has a lot of bills to pay and the amount of assets including cash do not exceed that value. Maintaining and monitoring solvency is a good way of preserving business. The measures of solvency help the assertion of whether a business is a going concern or not. In the banking industry, a solvent bank is identified by an excess of its total assets over its total liabilities (Muthoni, 2015).

2.1.2 Financial Performance

Financial performance refers to an organization's ability to generate and manage financial resources effectively, which is crucial for its sustainability and growth (Haddad & Bouri, 2022). According to Kanzari et al, (2022), financial performance is the measurement of an entity's profitability, where it assesses the capacity to generate earnings and income, typically through metrics such as net profit margins, return on assets (ROA), or return on equity (ROE). A second perspective emphasizes financial stability and liquidity, focusing on an organisation's ability to meet short-term financial obligations. In this context, financial performance is gauged through metrics like the current ratio, quick ratio, and working capital, which reflect an entity's ability to pay off its debts and cover day-to-day operational expenses (Tudose et al, 2022). Furthermore, another dimension of financial performance relates to growth and value creation. This perspective examines an entity's ability to increase its shareholder value over time, often using metrics like earnings per share (EPS) growth, market capitalization, and the price-to-earnings (P/E) ratio (Sddique et al, 2021).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Commercial Loan Theory

This theory was developed by Adam Smith in England during the 18th century. The commercial loan or the real bills doctrine theory states that a commercial bank should provide only short-term self-liquidating productive loans to business organizations. Loans meant to finance the production, and evolution of goods through the successive phases of production, storage, transportation, and distribution are considered as self-liquidating loans. This theory also states

that whenever commercial banks make short-term self-liquidating productive loans, the central bank should lend to the banks on the security of such short-term loans.

2.2.2 The Liabilities Management Theory

This theory was developed in the 1960s. According to this theory, there is no need for banks to grant self-liquidating loans and keep liquid assets because they can borrow reserve money in the money market in case of need. Wiley (2013) states that a bank can acquire reserves by creating additional liabilities against itself from different sources. These sources include the issuing of time certificates of deposit, borrowing from other commercial banks, borrowing from the central banks, raising capital funds by issuing shares, and plowing back profits.

2.2.3 Loanable Fund Theory

Wicksell (1930) states that the theory was put forward as the long-run theory of interest determination and is most applicable for explaining long-term rates of interest. The theory is an attempt at trying to identify the proximate causes of interest rate variation by analyzing the demand and supply of credit. The theory comes from the belief that those who save decide between consumption in the future now.

2.2.4 Theoretical Framework

This study discussed commercial loan theory, liability management theory, and loanable fund theory because of their relationship to the study. However, the study is anchored on commercial loan theory because it has to do with the liquidation of loans from the proceeds of goods and services produced by the company.

2.3 Empirical Review

Njure (2014) assessed the relationship between liquidity and profitability of non-financial companies listed on the Nairobi Stock Exchange. Correlation results showed a significant weak positive relationship between liquidity and profitability among listed non-financial companies in Kenya.

Patjoshi (2016) examined liquidity management and financial performance of selected steel companies in India from 2010 to 2014. Results from the study showed that liquidity has a significant effect on financial performance.

Obi-Nwosu et al (2017) investigated liquidity and corporate performance in Nigeria from 1984 to 2014. The study established that a significant negative short-term relationship exists between cash reserve ratio and performance, but no insignificant positive relationship between loan to deposit.

Abubakar (2015) examined the relationship between financial leverage and financial performance in Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. The study established that there is no significant relationship between debt ratio and financial performance proxied by return on equity.

Afolabi et al (2021) established that institutional efficiency has a positive impact on corporate performance in the Nigerian banking industry as evidenced by improvements in profitability, liquidity, and efficiency ratios.

Kinyonde et al (2021) found a positive and significant relationship between institutional quality and firm performance in East African Countries. Specifically, the result confirmed that

regulatory quality, rule of law, control of corruption, government effectiveness, and political stability have positive and significant effects on both the ROA and ROE of firms in East Africa.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

Ex-post facto research design is adopted in this study because data used for the study were of previous financial statements and cannot be manipulated.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population used in this study consisted of manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange (NSE) as of December 31, 2021. The companies were chosen because their financial statements are easily available on the Exchange.

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

Ten (10) companies with similar characteristics of size, legal status, geographical location, etc. were selected from the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) for this study. The companies studied were selected based on purposive sampling techniques and this was based on validity and availability of data. The companies selected for the study are Cadbury Nigeria Plc, Guinness Nigeria Plc, Nestle Nigeria Plc, Nigerian Bottling Co. Plc, Honeywell Flour Mills Plc, 7-up Bottling Co Plc. Others are Dangote Flour Mills, Dangote Cement Plc, P.Z Cussons Nigeria Plc and Lafarge Plc.

3.4 Data Source

The study used secondary data obtained from the audited annual reports of the companies sampled. Additional data were obtained from the websites of the companies and other publications of similar companies.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

The study used a multiple regression model to analyze the effect of corporate solvency on financial performance to establish and evaluate a cause-and-effect relationship.

3.6 Regression Model Specifications

This study adopts the following representative and regression models to examine performance and corporate solvency.

The model used for this study is as stated below:

$$ROA = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1X_1 + \alpha_2X_2 - \alpha_3X_3 - \alpha_4X_4 + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

α_0 is the intercept

$\alpha_{x(1-4)}$ will be the coefficients of the independent variables

μ_{it} Error term

“i” represents the individual companies.

“t” represents the time covered for this study it is in terms of years.

Table 4.1 Hausman Test Result

Test Summary	Chi-Sq Statistic	Chi-Sq. D.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	11.561163	4	0.0209

Source: Researcher’s study, 2024

Table 4.2 Regression Analysis

Variable	MODEL			
	Coefficient	Std Error	T-Stat.	Prob.
C	8.666956	1.391402	6.228936	0.0000
OPEF	-0.746204	0.375685	-1.986248	0.0502
CR	1.379982	0.859348	1.605848	0.1120
WCM	-0.003612	0.007869	-0.459002	0.6474
DE	-0.175401	0.143221	-1.224688	0.2240
R ²	0.767537			
Adj. R ²	0.732398			
F-Statistic	21.84247			
Prob. (F-Stat)	0.000000			
Observation	100			
Cross-sections	10			

Dependent Variable: ROA

*Significant at 5%

Source: Researcher’s study, 2024

$$ROA = \alpha + \alpha_1 OPEF_{it} + \alpha_2 CR_{it} - \alpha_3 WCM_{it} - \alpha_4 DE_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

$$ROA = 8.666956 - 0.746204 OPEF + 1.379982 CR - 0.003612 WCM - 0.175401 DE$$

Interpretation and Apriori Expectations

Table 4.1 shows the hausman test result with a P-value of 0.0209 which is lower than the acceptable 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis that random effect is suitable for this model is rejected. Indicating that the model should be estimated using fixed effect, thus fixed effect was used.

Table 4.2 shows the result of the regression estimate. The estimate of the regression in table 4.2 illustrates that OPEF, WCM, and DE hurt financial performance measured by Return on Assets (ROA), shown by the sign and size of the coefficients: $\alpha_1 = -0.746204 < 0$, $\alpha_3 = -0.003612 > 0$, $\alpha_4 = -0.175401 < 0$ respectively, while CR gives a positive influence evidenced by the size and sign of its coefficient at $\alpha_1 = 1.379982 < 0$. The size of the coefficient also implies a unit increase in OPEF, CR, WCM, and DE will lead to a 0.746204-unit decrease, a 1.379982-unit increase,

0.003612-unit decrease, and a 0.175401 decrease in the ROA. Therefore, the result is in line with the Apriori expectation for the CR, WCM and DE but not for the OPEF.

Also, 4.2 shows the adjusted R-square of the model, which illustrates that approximately 73.2% variation in ROA can be attributed to OPEF, CR, WCM, and DE, and the remaining 26.8% is caused by the explanatory variables not covered by this mode. Therefore, there exists a strong explanatory power for OPEF. This is verified by the p-value of the t-statistics at 0.000000 which is lower than the threshold of 5%. By this, the model is deemed as significant.

Thus, the negative impact of Operational Efficiency (OPEF), Working Capital Management (WCM), Debt/Equity Ratio (DE) and the positive impact of Current Ratio (CR) on Return on Assets (ROA) is statistically significant. So, the null hypothesis that Corporate Solvency has no significant influence on Returns on Assets is rejected.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

From the descriptive and empirical analyses, the following are the findings:

The statistical summary provided evidence of the variation in values of corporate solvency measured by Operational Efficiency, Current Ratio, Working Capital Management, and Debt/Equity and Financial Performance measured by Return on Assets for the period under study for the organizations sampled. This is revealed by the difference in the maximum and minimum values. This denotes that over the period under study, the solvency position of the business was fluctuating, and the financial performance was also fluctuating for the organizations sampled.

The estimate of the regression of the Operational Efficiency (OPEF), Current Ratio, working capital Management, and Debt/Equity has a positive influence on financial performance measured by Return on Assets (ROA) which agrees with the results of Kinyonde et al 2021. The estimate of the regression in Table 4.2 illustrates that OPEF, WCM, and DE have a negative significant impact on the ROA illustrated by the size of the coefficients: $\alpha_1 = -0.746204$, $\alpha_3 = -0.003612$, $\alpha_4 = -0.175401$ respectively, while CR gives a positive effect with its coefficient as $\alpha_2 = 1.379982$. The size of the coefficient also implies a unit increase in OPEF, CR, WCM, and DE will lead to a 0.746204-unit decrease, 1.379982-unit increase, 0.003612-unit decrease, and a 0.175401 decrease in the ROA. Therefore, the result is in line with the Apriori expectation for the CR, WCM and DE but not for the OPEF. The result also indicates that 73.2% of the variations in ROA can be attributed to fluctuations in the OPEF, CR, WCM, and DE, while the remaining 26.8% is attributable to factors outside the model. Thus, the model has strong explanatory power. This is confirmed by the p-value of the t-statistic at 0.000000 lower than the threshold of 5%. As such the model is statistically significant. Therefore, Operational Efficiency, Current Ratio, Working Capital Management, and Debt/Equity have significant effects on Financial Performance.

Thus, Operational Efficiency, Current Ratio, Working Capital Management, and Debt/Equity Ratio have a significant influence on Financial Performance.

In general, the regression estimates reveal that Operational Efficiency (OPEF) measured by the cost of goods sold divided by capital employed, Working Capital Management (WCM) measured by the cash conversion cycle and leverage measured by Debt/Equity Ratio have

negative influences on the GEOMEAN geometric mean of the ROA. However, the p-value of the f-statistic at 0.00000 lower than the acceptable 5% level of significance indicates the model is statistically significant. Therefore, Operational Efficiency (OPE), Working Capital Management, and Debt/Equity Ratio have a positive significant influence and Current Ratio has a positive influence on Financial Performance measured by the GEOMEAN of ROA, ROCE, and ROE. Hence, corporate solvency has a significant influence on the financial performance of manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

This study has investigated the impact of corporate solvency on the financial performance of 10 sampled manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian stock exchange over 10 years, using selected proxies as the explanatory variables. The study denotes that the various measures of corporate solvency influence financial performance in different ways, being that liquidity has a positive influence while operational efficiency, working capital management, and leverage harm the financial performance with the individual and aggregate influence of the proxies of corporate solvency being statistically significant.

Furthermore, the aggregate effect of all proxies for corporate solvency indicates a significant effect of 0.00000 (Probability of F-Stat) on the GEOMEAN which is the measure of financial performance. Each of the proxies has a significant influence on the financial performance.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The management board of the organizations examined in this study should monitor closely the factors that affect financial performance considered in the study which are liquidity that has a positive influence on the financial performance of their businesses and should be improved upon to reflect on the performance of the business. Other exogenous variables that will significantly affect the performance of manufacturing companies in Nigeria should be focused on.
2. Management of manufacturing companies in Nigeria should put in place a liquidity policy that will enhance the profitability of their companies.

References

- Abubakar, A. (2015). Relationship between financial leverage and financial performance of DMBs in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 3(10), 759-778
- Afolabi, A., Adesina, A. & Amaihian, A.B. (2021). Institutional efficiency and corporate performance: An empirical study of the Nigerian banking industry. *Journal of African Business*, 22(2), 167-186
- AlGhusin, N. (2015). The impact of financial leverage, growth and size on profitability of Jordanian Industrial Listed Companies. *Research Journal of Finance Accounting*, 6(16), 86-93.
- Alkhatib, K. (2012). The determinants of leverage of listed companies. *International Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 3(24), 78-83
- Almajali, Y.A., Alamro, A., & Al-Soub, Y. (2012). Factors affecting financial performance of Jordanian Insurance Companies listed at Amman Stock Exchange. *Journal of Management Research*, 4(2), 226-289
- Banafa, A.S., Muturi, W., & Ngugi, K. (2015). The liquidity factor in the financial performance of non-listed financial firms in Kenya. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(7), 112-118
- Chariou, M., Elfani, M., & Lois, P. (2010). The effect of working capital management on firm's profitability: Empirical evidence from an Emerging Market. *Journal of Business & Economics Research*, 14(3), 111-118.
- Haddad, A. & Bouri, A. (2022). The impact of Sharia Advisory Board characteristics on the financial performance of Islamic banks. *Cogent Economics and Finance*, 10(1), 41-55
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2022.2062911>
- Kakanda, M.M., Bello, A.B., & Abba, M. (2016). Effect of capital structure on performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 7(8), 211-219. DOI: www.iiste.org

- Kanzari, A., Rasmussen, J., Nehler, H. & Ingelsson, F. (2022). How financial performance is addressed considering the transition to circular business models- A systematic literature review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 376, 85-103
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clepro.2022.134134>
- Khidmat, W.B. & Rehman, M.U. (2014). Impact of liquidity and solvency on profitability of chemical sector in Pakistan. *Economics Management Innovation Journal*, 6(3), 34-67
- Kinyonde, A., Maganga, A.M. & Nwakalika, S. (2021). Institutional quality and firm performance in East African Countries. *Journal of African Business*, 22(3), 361-376
- Muthoni, M.R. (2015). The effect of liquidity and solvency on the profitability of banks in Kenya. *Business and Economic Horizon*, 4(1), 52-69
- Njure, K.C. (2014). The relationship between liquidity and profitability of non-financial companies listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange. *Business Theory and Practice*, 15(4), 351-361
- Obi-Nwosu, V.O., Okaro, C., Ogbonna, K.S. & Atsanan, A.N. (2017). Effect of liquidity on performance of DMBs. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering and Management Research*, 2(4), 64-73
- Patjoshi, P.K. (2016). A study on liquidity management and financial performance of Selected Steel Companies in India. *International Journal of Advanced Information Science and Technology*, 51(7), 108-117 <https://doi.org/10.15693/ijaist/2016v517108-117>
- Siddique, M.A., Akhtaruzzaman, M., Rashid, A. & Hammami, H. (2021). Carbon disclosure performance and and financial performance: International evidence. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 75, 418-442 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2021.101734>
- Tudose, M.B., Rusu, V.D. & Avasilcai, S. (2022). Financial performance-determinants and interdependencies between measurement indicators. *Business Management and Economics Engineering*, 20(1), 65-83 <https://doi.org/10.3846/bmee.2022.16732>
- Wicksell, K. (1930). Value, capital, and rent. *The Scandinavian Journal of Economics*. 80(2), 129- 134